

Efficient calculation of the pseudo-inverse when the nullspace is known

L. Lindegren
Lund Observatory
10 August 1995

1. Introduction

This note is concerned with the practical calculation of the pseudo-inverse of a singular normal equations matrix, $\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A}$, for which the nullspace is known. This case arises in certain problems where the observations are invariant with respect to a known set of transformations of the unknowns, such as a shift of origin. The nullspace corresponds exactly to the (linearised) transformations under which the data are invariant. Of course, the method described here cannot be used if the singularity is caused by a lack of data, or by improper design of the experiment. But in that case it is usually not very meaningful to use more sophisticated methods (such as SVD) either.

2. Calculation of the pseudo-inverse

Let n be the number of unknowns and $r > 0$ the dimension of the nullspace, so that $\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A}$ is a symmetric, non-negative definite matrix of size $n \times n$ and rank $n - r$. Furthermore, let $\mathbf{V}$ be an $n \times r$ matrix whose columns are orthogonal unit vectors spanning the nullspace (I return later to the question how to construct this matrix), and $\mathbf{U}$ the $n \times (n - r)$ matrix of orthogonal unit vectors spanning the complement to the nullspace. The singular value decomposition (SVD) of the normal equations matrix can then be written

$$\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U} & \mathbf{V} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{S} & \mathbf{0}_{(n-r) \times r} \\ \mathbf{0}_{r \times (n-r)} & \mathbf{0}_{r \times r} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}' \\ \mathbf{V}' \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{S} = \text{diag}(s_1 \dots s_{n-r})$ is the diagonal matrix of the positive singular values ($s_1 \geq s_2 \geq \dots \geq s_{n-r} > 0$) and $\mathbf{0}_{\mu \times \nu}$ are null matrices of appropriate dimensions. The pseudo-inverse is given by

$$(\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^+ = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U} & \mathbf{V} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{S}^{-1} & \mathbf{0}_{(n-r) \times r} \\ \mathbf{0}_{r \times (n-r)} & \mathbf{0}_{r \times r} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}' \\ \mathbf{V}' \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

For any positive number, $\beta > 0$, we can construct the symmetric auxiliary matrix

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U} & \mathbf{V} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{S} & \mathbf{0}_{(n-r) \times r} \\ \mathbf{0}_{r \times (n-r)} & \beta \mathbf{I}_r \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}' \\ \mathbf{V}' \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A} + \beta \mathbf{V}\mathbf{V}' \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{I}_r$ is the identity matrix of order r . Clearly $\mathbf{Q}$ is *positive definite*, so that an efficient algorithm such as Cholesky can be used to compute its inverse, $\mathbf{Q}^{-1}$. The latter can also be written

$$\mathbf{Q}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U} & \mathbf{V} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{S}^{-1} & \mathbf{0}_{(n-r) \times r} \\ \mathbf{0}_{r \times (n-r)} & \frac{1}{\beta} \mathbf{I}_r \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}' \\ \mathbf{V}' \end{pmatrix} = (\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^+ + \frac{1}{\beta} \mathbf{V}\mathbf{V}'. \quad (4)$$

Combining the last two equations gives the following simple result:

$$(\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^+ = (\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A} + \beta \mathbf{V}\mathbf{V}')^{-1} - \frac{1}{\beta} \mathbf{V}\mathbf{V}'. \quad (5)$$

How should one choose β in the above formula? In principle, the result is independent of the chosen value, but in practice it has some influence on the rounding errors. It is reasonable to assume that rounding errors are best under control if β is chosen to minimise the condition number of $\mathbf{Q}$. The condition number is usually defined as the ratio of the largest to the smallest singular value. Choosing β anywhere in the range from s_{n-r} to s_1 will clearly minimise the condition number of $\mathbf{Q}$. In particular, the mean of the positive singular values appears to be a good choice. Using the well-known theorem that the trace of a square matrix equals the sum of its eigenvalues, we arrive at the following simple recipe:

$$\beta = \frac{1}{n-r} \sum_{i=1}^n (\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})_{ii}. \quad (6)$$

3. Determination of the nullspace

The nullspace of $\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A}$ is the same as that of $\mathbf{A}$, and it consists of all non-zero n -vectors $\mathbf{a}$ such that $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0}_{n \times 1}$. If r linearly independent null vectors $\mathbf{a}_i$, $i = 1, \dots, r$ can be found, then one may construct the column vectors in $\mathbf{V}$ for instance by means of the Gram-Schmidt orthonormalisation algorithm:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v}_1 &= \langle \mathbf{a}_1 \rangle \\ \mathbf{v}_2 &= \langle \mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{v}_1(\mathbf{v}'_1 \mathbf{a}_2) \rangle \\ \mathbf{v}_3 &= \langle \mathbf{a}_3 - \mathbf{v}_1(\mathbf{v}'_1 \mathbf{a}_3) - \mathbf{v}_2(\mathbf{v}'_2 \mathbf{a}_3) \rangle \\ &\vdots \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where the angular brackets denote vector length normalisation, $\langle \mathbf{x} \rangle = \mathbf{x}(\mathbf{x}'\mathbf{x})^{-1/2}$. (Numerically superior orthonormalisation algorithms can be found in standard matrix software libraries.)

How can we find a set of linearly independent null vectors? This requires some consideration of the problem at hand. As an example I will take the equations described by S. Loiseau in *Global astrometry with OSI* (submitted to A&A, July 1995). In that problem, the unknowns consist of the celestial coordinates (α, δ) both of the stars (represented by unit vectors $\vec{S}$) and of the interferometer baselines (represented by vectors $\vec{B}$); the measured quantities are the delays $d = \vec{B} \cdot \vec{S} + c$. The delay offset (c) and baseline length (B) are supposed to be known from the metrology.

Clearly the quantity $\vec{B} \cdot \vec{S}$ is invariant with respect to an arbitrary rigid rotation of the system of celestial coordinates. An arbitrary rotation ($\vec{\epsilon}$) can be parametrised by three numbers, such as the coordinates of the rotation vector along the cartesian axes of the celestial system, $\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \epsilon_z$. The nullspace is therefore of dimension $r = 3$, and a set of null vectors can be

constructed by considering how each unknown is changed by small rotations about each of the three axes. The following first-order expressions are easily verified:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\alpha \cos \delta &= (-\epsilon_x \cos \alpha - \epsilon_y \sin \alpha) \sin \delta + \epsilon_z \cos \delta \\ \Delta\delta &= \epsilon_x \sin \alpha - \epsilon_y \cos \alpha\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

which leads to the following table for the correspondence between the elements of $\mathbf{x}$ (the column matrix of unknowns) and the three linearly independent null vectors $\mathbf{a}_i$:

element of $\mathbf{x}$	corresponding element of		
	$\mathbf{a}_1$	$\mathbf{a}_2$	$\mathbf{a}_3$
$(\Delta\alpha \cos \delta)_S$	$-\sin \delta_S \cos \alpha_S$	$-\sin \delta_S \sin \alpha_S$	$\cos \delta_S$
$(\Delta\delta)_S$	$\sin \alpha_S$	$-\cos \alpha_S$	0
$(\Delta\alpha \cos \delta)_B$	$-\sin \delta_B \cos \alpha_B$	$-\sin \delta_B \sin \alpha_B$	$\cos \delta_B$
$(\Delta\delta)_B$	$\sin \alpha_B$	$-\cos \alpha_B$	0

4. Remarks concerning the software implementation

The elementary algorithms needed to calculate the pseudo-inverse, in particular the vector orthonormalisation [Eq. (7)] and matrix inversion by the Cholesky method, can be found in standard software libraries. Nevertheless, it should be noted that these algorithms are extremely simple, fast and stable. Together they can probably be implemented in less than 100 Fortran statements. Two other properties contribute to the computational efficiency of the method:

First, all the calculations involving large matrices (of dimension $n \times n$ and even $n \times r$) can be made 'in place', requiring no intermediate storage. Secondly, the $n \times n$ matrices are symmetric and therefore only require $n(n-1)/2$ reals for their storage, provided vector subscripting is used (i.e., the upper-diagonal part of the symmetric matrix is stored as a single vector). The algorithms are well suited for vector subscripting; moreover, the most time consuming part (Cholesky inversion) operates with at most two columns at a time, which is normally handled quite efficiently by the virtual memory management.

The total storage requirement throughout the process is therefore about $n(n-1)/2 + rn$ reals (where rn reals are needed for the initial null vectors and subsequently for $\mathbf{V}$). The operation count is dominated by the Cholesky inversion and is of the order of $2n^3/3$ multiplications and additions. It is therefore likely that up to a few thousand unknowns can be handled entirely within the primary memory of a typical workstation, and that the computing time for such a task will be a few minutes.